

A 10-step guide to organizing your preprint event

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1

Shape your idea

Think about the topic and main goals for the event. Consider the questions below as you develop your idea:

What is the goal of the event? What would you like to achieve?

Do you want to raise awareness around preprints? Then use a presentation or panel discussion format. Is the aim to build skills around preprints among attendees? For this choose a workshop or similar format with interactive and practical content.

Who is your audience?

- A broad audience including researchers and others at your institution (e.g. librarians or research administrators)? Or is the focus only on researchers?
- Audiences from broad disciplinary backgrounds and career stages, or rather from a specific discipline or career stage (e.g. early career researchers)?
- Will the audience be familiar with preprints or relatively new to the topic?

What is the main topic?

There are different topic options:

- An introduction to preprints
- Benefits of preprints and things to bear in mind
- Trends and practices in specific disciplines or communities
- Preprints and open science

How will you handle the organization?

Consider having co-organizers for the event. Do you have collaborators who may be interested? There may also be groups at your institution whom you could approach to collaborate such as a local postdoc organization or librarians.

Create a document to capture your thoughts about the event. This will allow you to refer back to your goals as preparations proceed and to have all the information available for your co-organizers.

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Develop the event plan

Consider the event format according to your goals and decide whether the event will be a lecture, a panel discussion, an interactive workshop, or another format. You should also consider the length of the event: for lectures or panel discussions a one-hour format usually works well, workshops may require longer (e.g. 90 minutes) depending on the activities to complete with attendees.

Start a draft description for the event anchored around your main topic. This draft will help you shape the main message for attendees as well as themes or activities to cover during the event.

Event preparation document template**Goals**

By the end of the workshop attendees would:

Audience

(E.g. researchers, early-career researchers, librarians and/or research administrators; any disciplinary focus? Level of familiarity with preprints?)

Event information

- Format (e.g. presentation, workshop, panel discussion etc.)
- Date
- Location (online, in-person and if so at which venue, hybrid)
- Registration (link to where attendees can register to the event e.g. Zoom, Eventbrite etc.)
- Title
- Brief description

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Get buy in

For events hosted at your institution, it can be really helpful to garner support from other researchers or groups, as they can help you shape the event, put you in touch with potential speakers and help with promotion:

- Discuss the event with your supervisor or other researchers at your institution who have posted preprints or are interested in open science.

- Pitch the event to relevant reps in the university e.g. does the library run events for faculty, would they be interested in collaborating? You could also speak to your head of department or the dean of the university about your proposal.

In addition to getting support internally from your institution, you can also seek broader local support, to either collaborate organizing the event or to help promote it:

- Are there any groups active in open science in your city or region you could contact?
- Are there any local or global events you could leverage to increase the visibility of your event, e.g. local science festivals, Open Access Week.

Template to approach groups for collaboration or support

New Message

Recipients

Subject

Dear [group contact name],

I hope you are doing well.

I am [your details, name and a note about your position].

I am reaching out to you because I am planning an event about preprints [event title, description]. Given the work of [group name] [with the local researcher community/in open science/relevant group focus], I wanted to contact you to explore whether you would be interested in collaborating in this event.

The event will take place on [Date, time, venue] and is open to the public/faculty members from [institution name]. I would be delighted if [group name] would like to be involved in [the organization/supporting the promotion] of the event.

I would love to talk with you and share a bit more about the plans for the event, and learn more about your activities to explore common areas of interest. Would it be possible to schedule a brief meeting so we can discuss further? Please let me know when would be suitable for you over the next two weeks and I'll be happy to schedule the call.

Thank you for your time, I look forward to hearing from you.

With best wishes,

Send

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Work out the logistics

Once you have the initial plan for the event and any necessary buy in from your institution, start working through the logistical details:

- Event date - you could start with a range of dates and select the date with the speakers according to their availability. If your event will be in person, do make sure to check room options and availability for the possible dates.
- For in-person events:
 - Check for any audiovisual materials that will be needed e.g. laptop and projector if there are any presentations, microphones for speakers and the audience.
 - Drinks and snacks can be a good way to attract additional attendees. If the venue provides catering, check whether they need an estimate for the number of attendees and by when. If the venue does not provide catering, consider an alternative option to provide drinks and snacks.

ASAPbio**ASAPbio Community**

If you are a member of the ASAPbio Community, you can apply for support by ASAPbio for any expenses from your project related to equipment, printing for hand out materials or catering for the event. For more information on what type of funds ASAPbio can support and the application form, see:

asapbio.org/community-projects

- If the event will take place online, consider what online platform you will use to host the event (e.g. Zoom, Microsoft Teams).
 - If you collaborate with a team at your university you may be able to use their platform for online activities.
 - Once you have selected the platform, set up a registration page for the event and see if you can get help for any tech aspects of the event hosting.

ASAPbio

If you need support with online hosting for the event, you can also contact ASAPbio and we'd be happy to host the event on the ASAPbio Zoom, and help set up the registration page and any Zoom items.

In parallel to the speaker invitations, you should select a Chair - that is, the person who will introduce the event and the speakers, handle the questions from the audience, and facilitate the discussion if there will be a panel discussion. You or one of the organizers can act as Chair for the event, alternatively, there may be a person from the institution whom you'd like to approach for this role e.g. the dean or head of the department if they expressed support for your event.

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Set the event details

Keep a tally of confirmed speakers as they reply to your invitations. If anyone declines, contact the alternative speaker you had for that perspective. Once you have a confirmed line up of speakers, if you still need to narrow down the date from a range of options, contact all the speakers about their preferred date/time, to settle the event date.

Follow up over email with the speakers to confirm the event date and time - it can be useful to also send them a calendar invite as a placeholder. In the same communication, ask the speakers for their title and a photo, so that you can use this in the promotional materials for the event.

Once you have the chair and speaker line up, you can finalize the registration page and promotional materials for the event.

- For in-person events: Prepare an event poster to print and use for promotion throughout the institution. You could also develop a pull-up banner to use on the day, and you can contact ASAPbio about having [preprint stickers](#) or a preprint brochure to distribute to attendees.

- For both in-person and online events: it can be useful to prepare a banner/image to promote the event via social media channels (e.g. Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn) or messaging groups such as Whatsapp.

Ensure that you set up registration in a way that allows you to collect registration numbers and ideally send reminders to registered attendees, a few possible options are:

- Zoom allows you to collect registrations and also to send automatic reminders to registered attendees.
- Eventbrite collects registrations and sends out reminders, this platform is a good option to collect registrations for in-person events.
- If you set up registration via Google forms, we recommend that you send out email reminders to registered attendees one week before and one day before the event. You can also send registrants calendar invites for the event.

Brochure
Print a preprint brochure to distribute to attendees

Pull-up banner
You could develop a pull-up banner to use on the day

Promotion
Prepare a banner to promote the event via social media channels or messaging groups

ASAPbio WEBINAR

The impact of preprints for early career researchers

Register at tinyurl.com/preprintsforecra

October	5pm BST
6	Noon EDT
2021	9am PDT
	1pm BRT

Speakers:

- João Victor Cabral Costa, University of São Paulo, Brazil
- Iain Chesseman, Whitehead Institute, US
- Hannah Hope, Wellcome, UK
- Malisa Jadavji, McMaster University, US & Carleton University, Canada
- Moderator: Keti Zeka, University College London, UK

ONLINE WORKSHOP

Research assessment and preprints in India

A workshop for Indian researchers
Discussing current assessment frameworks and the opportunities provided by preprints

TUESDAY JUNE 7, 2022
5.00pm - 6.30pm IST

REGISTER TODAY

ASAPbio

In collaboration with:

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Promote the event

Disseminate information about the event on institutional channels (e.g. internal newsletters, postdoc or student groups) and on social media. We recommend initiating promotion at least 4 weeks before the event date. Ask the speakers and local groups you have been in touch with to promote the event, and tag ASAPbio or other open science organizations in your social media posts to help spread the word.

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Do your prep

If the event will be hosted in person, take time to visit the venue and do a quick check of the room to get an idea of the set up and the audiovisual tools you will use on the day.

Schedule a brief meeting or call (30 minutes) with all the speakers to discuss the running of the event, and to check in regarding:

- The format and timings
- The topics that each speaker will talk about; for panel discussion events, you can brainstorm some questions for the panel with the chair and the speakers.
- Provide an overview of the logistical details: venue (or online platform if online), how long in advance of the event start you would like speakers to arrive etc.

If you are planning to do live tweeting (or some other form of live coverage) during the event, document who will handle this and make sure they have all the information they need e.g. social media handles for the speakers.

**Promote
the event**

**Initiate promotion
at least 4 week
before the
event date**

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Run the event

On the day of the event, make sure to arrive early, so that you can welcome the speakers, and manage entry to the venue for attendees, if required. Bring a colleague with you, so that they can welcome attendees and/or address any attendee questions if you are busy setting up the speakers. For in-person events we recommend that you are at the venue 30 minutes early; for online events, it is usually enough to open the online platform 15-20 minutes in advance for any final tech checks i.e microphone, camera and screen sharing for speakers.

Start the event on time, but allow enough intro time to ensure that any attendees who may join a few minutes after the time do not miss any critical information. If you are not chairing the event, do a brief welcome to attendees and then hand over to the Chair to get the event going.

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Share the learnings

Once the event is done, send a brief thank-you note to the speakers for their time and contribution.

If your event was hosted as part of activities within the institution, consider sharing a brief form with attendees to gather their feedback on the event and on additional topics about preprints or science communication that they may be interested in. This can be done in the last few minutes of the event itself, or as a follow-up request via email.

Consider sharing a summary about the event via a blog post, discussing the highlights and learnings from the presentations and/or discussion. If the event was recorded you can share the recording as well as any other materials (e.g. slides, links to resources) via the blog post.

